

The following material provides additional information to Section

3. Research Method

- Interview Protocol
- Participant Overview

4. Result

- Coding Scheme

Interview Protocol: Understanding Negative Contingencies in Process Mining Initiatives

Definition and Context:

- **Definition of Contingency:** In information systems (IS), a contingency refers to a specific condition, factor, or circumstance that influences the potential for achieving value from an information system implementation. Contingencies can be positive or negative, and often vary based on the organization's unique environment.
- **Difference from Critical Success Factors (CSFs):** Unlike critical success factors, which are essential for success, contingencies are not tied directly to success or failure. They either enable or constrain the realization of value, impacting the outcomes in nuanced ways. In many cases, organizations do not have a means to control contingency factors. They can only do their best to limit (in the case of negative) or foster (in the case of positive) the effect of contingencies on the IS implementation outcomes.
- **Why Contingencies Matter?**
 - **Organizational Fit:** Contingencies reveal how specific conditions influence IS implementation, making it essential to understand unique organizational contexts.
 - **Risk and Resource Management:** Contingencies help in identifying risks and ensuring resources are strategically allocated for IS implementation, allowing for better preparation and adaptability.

Interview Objectives:

1. To verify the existence and relevance of a list of negative contingencies in process mining implementation identified by the researchers.
 2. To explore other potential negative contingencies that might affect the value conversion in process mining implementation.
 3. To gather insights on how practitioners perceive and manage the identified negative contingencies in process mining projects.
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Recording Instruction

I would like to record our interview to simplify the note-taking process and ensure that no information is lost. Your answers and comments will be processed and reflected in any research outcome (e.g., **published articles**) anonymously. The information you provide will only be used for this research. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may stop at any time.

Background Questions

1. I will ask general questions about your background and understanding of the topic. If you have already filled in the Google form that I sent you beforehand, this will be buried.
 2. Can you tell us about your experiences in the process mining initiatives ?
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Part 1: Understanding Negative Contingencies

1. Contingency Concept Familiarity:

- Do you understand the concept of negative contingencies in IS implementation as discussed earlier? Are there any questions or areas where you would like further clarification or explanation?

2. Specific Negative Contingencies:

- We have identified 9 negative contingencies that may impact process mining. Please look at the materials we will send before the interview, feel free to contact us with any questions. There are summarized below:
 - *Distributed Development Teams*: Coordination issues across geographically dispersed teams.
 - *Result Expectation*: Unrealistic expectations from new tools that do not align with immediate outcomes.
 - *Data Privacy*: Challenges with compliance with data protection laws.
 - *IoT Data Problems*: Issues with processing and standardizing IoT data.
 - *Disconnection Between Insight and Improvement*: Lack of actionable insights following analysis.
 - *Sharing Success Story*: Misalignment in sharing best practices across different teams or business units.

- *Hidden Task*: Unrecorded tasks that affect process visibility and accuracy.
 - *Organizational Alignment*: Challenges in aligning various organizational components with the process mining initiative.
 - *Architecture Integration Choice*: Difficulties in integrating process mining with existing systems and infrastructure.
- **Question**: Did you experience these contingencies in the process mining implementation projects you have been involved in? and how to manage it?

3. **Other Negative Contingencies** and how to manage?

- **Question**: Are there other contingencies beyond those listed, that you've encountered during process mining implementation?
- **Question**: How did you deal with negative contingencies that you encountered?

Part 3: Distinguishing from Critical Success Factors

- **Question**: Do you believe there is an overlap with Critical Success Factors, or do you see them as distinct influences on the process mining journey?

Participant Overview for Expert Interview

ID	Industry	Continent	Role	Experience	Gender (M/F)	Education
I1	IT Service and Consulting	Oceania	PM Consultant	3-5 years	F	Master
I2	PM Technology Provider	Asia (+North America)	Director of Value Engineering	>5 years	M	Bachelor
I3	IT Service and Consulting	Europe	Product Manager	1-3 years	M	Doctoral
I4	PM Technology Provider	Asia	Lead Consultant	1-3 years	F	Master
I5	PM Technology Provider	Asia	Senior Ecosystem Consultant	3-5 years	M	Master
I6	IT Services & Consulting	Asia	Senior Research Engineer	1-3 years	F	Doctoral
I7	IT Services & Consulting	Oceania	Manager	>5 years	F	Doctoral
I8	Retail	Oceania	Data Driven Innovator	>5 years	F	Master
I9	Retail	Asia	PM Analyst	1-3 years	F	Master

1st Researcher – Initial Coding for Expert Interview

Code	Negative Contingency	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9
C	<i>Did you experience these contingencies?</i>									
C1	1. Distributed team	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
C2	2. Result Expectation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
C3	3. Data Privacy	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A
C4	4. IOT Data	N/A								
C5	5. Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Yes								
C6	6. Sharing Success Story	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	N/A
C7	7. Hidden Task	Yes	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
C8	8. Organizational Alignment	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
C9	9. Architecture Integration Choice	N/A	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
D	<i>Do you see the distinction between negative contingency with critical success factor?</i>	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	N/A

2st Researcher – Initial Coding for Expert Interview

Code	Negative Contingency	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9
C	<i>Did you experience these contingencies</i>									
C1	1. Distributed team	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes
C2	2. Result Expectation	Yes								
C3	3. Data Privacy	Yes	N/A							
C4	4. IOT Data	N/A								
C5	5. Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Yes								
C6	6. Sharing Success Story	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	N/A
C7	7. Hidden Task	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
C8	8. Organizational Alignment	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
C9	9. Architecture Integration Choice	N/A	Yes	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
D	<i>Do you see the distinction between negative contingency with critical success factor?</i>	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	N/A

Recap : N/A and No will be calculated as N, and Yes as Y

Code	Negative Contingency	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9
C1	Distributed team	N/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y
C2	Result Expectation	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y
C3	Data Privacy	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/Y
C4	IoT Data	N/N								
C5	Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Y/Y								
C6	Sharing Success Story	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/N
C7	Hidden Task	Y/Y	N/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y
C8	Organizational Alignment	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y
C9	Architecture Integration Choice	N/N	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y
D	Distinction with CSF	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	Y/Y	N/N	Y/Y	N/N

To assess the consistency of the deductive coding process, inter-coder reliability was measured using Cohen’s Kappa. This metric adjusts the raw agreement score to account for the agreement that might happen by chance.

Observed Agreement (Po)

Out of a total of N = 90 coding decisions (10 codes × 9 interviewees), both coders agreed on 64 cases with 'Yes/Yes' and 21 cases with 'No/No' classifications.

$$Po = (64 + 21) / 90 = 85 / 90 \approx 0.944$$

Expected Agreement (Pe)

The proportion of Yes and No assignments by each coder is calculated below:

Coder	Yes	No	Total
Coder 1	64	26	90
Coder 2	69	21	90

$$P1_Yes = 64 / 90 \approx 0.711, P1_No = 26/90 \approx 0.268$$

$$P2_Yes = 69 / 90 \approx 0.767, P2_No = 21/90 \approx 0.233$$

$$Pe = (0.711 \times 0.767) + (0.268 \times 0.233) = 0.546 + 0.067 = 0.613$$

Cohen’s Kappa Calculation

$$\kappa = (Po - Pe) / (1 - Pe) = (0.944 - 0.613) / (1 - 0.613) = 0.331 / 0.387 \approx 0.857$$

Interpretation

According to the interpretation scale by Landis and Koch (1977), Cohen’s Kappa of 0.857 indicates almost perfect. This confirms that coders were consistent in applying the predefined deductive codes, demonstrating high reliability of the qualitative data analysis.

Kappa Value	Strength of Agreement
< 0.00	Poor
0.00–0.20	Slight
0.21–0.40	Fair
0.41–0.60	Moderate
0.61–0.80	Substantial (Good)
0.81–1.00	Almost Perfect

Appendix – Mapping of Additional Observations to Existing Contingencies

The following table presents additional observations gathered during the expert interviews. These inputs were assessed against the existing set of negative contingencies derived from thematic analysis. Based on the coding and conceptual alignment, none of these items qualified as entirely new contingencies. Instead, they were mapped to existing categories or recognized as implementation challenges already reflected in CSFs or maturity considerations.

New Contingency	Mapped Category	Rationale
Engage with stakeholders	Organizational Alignment	Refers to collaboration and stakeholder buy-in
Structure to support change	Organizational Alignment	Part of the need is to assign ownership of value or benefit to the PM change.
Change in executive sponsor	Organizational Alignment	Specific instance of top management commitment or volatility
Identify challenges at the beginning.	CSF (Planning & Scoping)	Describes best practices, not a contingency
Having measurements to track	Result Expectation	Relates to expectations and KPI alignment
Data Quality	Partially addressed under Hidden Task and IoT Data but better understood as a broader data readiness concern.	Covered under the existing data readiness capability, this should be considered a Critical Success Factor or a maturity dimension.
Compliance	Data Privacy	May overlap with regulatory or legal access issues
Unrealized benefit	—	An outcome, not an antecedent condition
Time zone	Distributed Development Team	Operational barrier under geographic distribution
Language Barrier	Distributed Development Team	Communication barrier, context-specific within global or multilingual teams
Analysis doesn't find anything.	Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Reflects low actionability of insights
Unclear starting point	Result Expectation	Relates to scoping and ambiguity in PM use cases
Organization maturity	—	A framing layer, not a contingency itself
Defining the value	Result Expectation	Part of the goal clarity and project justification issues
No strategic plan or PM focus	Organizational Alignment	Links to prioritization and leadership direction